

1 Temperature and water stress during conditioning and incubation
2 phase affecting *Orobanche crenata* seed germination and radicle
3 growth
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8
9 **ABSTRACT**

10 *Orobanche crenata* is a holoparasitic plant that is potentially devastating to crop yield
11 of legume species. Soil temperature and humidity are known to affect seed germination,
12 however, the extent of their influence on germination and radicle growth of those of *O.*
13 *crenata* is largely unknown. In this work, we studied the effects of temperature, water
14 potential (Ψ_t) and the type of water stress (matric or osmotic) on *O. crenata* seeds
15 during conditioning and incubation periods. We found that seeds germinated between 5
16 and 30°C during both periods, with a maximum around 20°C. Germination increased
17 with increasing Ψ_t from -1.2 to 0 MPa during conditioning and incubation periods.
18 Likewise, seed germination increased logarithmically with length of conditioning period
19 until 40 days. The impact of the type of water stress on seed germination was similar,
20 although the radicle growth of seeds under osmotic stress was lower than under matric
21 stress, what could explain the lowest infestation of *Orobanche* spp. in regions
22 characterized by saline soil. The data in this study will be useful to forecast infection of
23 host roots by *O. crenata*.

24 **Keywords:** broomrape, water potential, matric and osmotic stress

25

1 INTRODUCTION

2 The holoparasitic weed *Orobanche crenata* Forsk. is responsible for important crop
3 losses across the Mediterranean and West Asia where it parasitizes mainly Fabaceae
4 species such as faba bean (*Vicia faba*), grasspea (*Lathyrus sativus*), lentil (*Lens
5 culinaris*), pea (*Pisum sativum*), and vetches (*Vicia* spp.), but also Umbelliferae such as
6 carrot (*Daucus carota*) (Grenz and Sauerborn, 2007; Parker, 2009). Because each
7 *Orobanche* plant produces thousands of minute seeds that persist viable in the soil for
8 many years increasing the parasite seedbank in the soil and because infection and
9 pathogenic process takes place underground (Joel *et al.*, 2007) the effective control of
10 this weedy species is extremely difficult (Rubiales *et al.*, 2009).

11 *Orobanche* seeds germinate under favorable environmental conditions and the presence
12 of chemical stimulants in the root exudates of proper plant species (Fernández-Aparicio
13 *et al.*, 2009). Before this, the *Orobanche* seeds are in an inactive state. Only after a
14 conditioning period of several days that follows seed imbibition, *O. crenata* seeds can
15 respond to germination stimulants (Van Hezewijk *et al.*, 1993). However, this is not the
16 case for other *Orobanche* species such as *O. cumana* and *O. aegyptiaca* (syn.
17 *Phelipanche aegyptiaca*) in which this conditioning helps, but is not essential for
18 stimulant receptivity (Plakhine *et al.*, 2009). During the conditioning period,
19 temperature (T), water potential (Ψ_t), oxygen availability and growth regulators are
20 known to affect the seed viability of several species of *Orobanche* and their germination
21 response (Van Hezewijk *et al.*, 1993; Kebreab and Murdoch, 1999; Gibot-Leclerc *et al.*,
22 2004; Song *et al.*, 2005).

23 Environmental factors, especially T and Ψ_t , affect the germination of conditioned seeds
24 during incubation after exposure to germination stimulants (Kebreab and Murdoch,
25 2000). Once the parasitic seed germination is induced, an infective radicle arises from
26 the seed coat and grows, following a positive gradient of germination stimulants until
27 the host root, to which it can adhere and penetrate (Fernández-Aparicio *et al.*, 2010).
28 Therefore, the seeds, which show a large radicle, reach far roots what increases the
29 infection efficiency. Temperature and Ψ_t can also affect the seed radicle elongation
30 (Dodd and Donovan, 1999). Nevertheless, the impact of both T and Ψ_t on radicle
31 elongation of *Orobanche* seeds are little understood. This information is essential for

1 the development of germination and infection submodels, critical components to
2 forecast effects of *O. crenata* on legume hosts.

3 Water potential quantifies the tendency of water to move from one point to another. In
4 the soil, Ψ_t is mainly the sum of: (i) the gravitational potential (Ψ_g); (ii) osmotic
5 potential (Ψ_o) as a consequence of the presence of ionic changes due to salts and non-
6 ionically due to water binding by components on plant parts or other solutes; and (iii)
7 matric potential (Ψ_m) caused by water adsorption and surface tension phenomena in soil
8 (Papendick and Campbell 1980). Whereas Ψ_m and Ψ_o can change substantially and
9 therefore affect seed germination, gravitational potential is determined solely by
10 elevation of a point to some arbitrary reference point being negligible in near points (i.e.
11 seed and adjacent water). In non-saline soils, Ψ_m is the dominant component (Papendick
12 and Campbell 1980; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2011).

13 Furthermore, seed germination is differently affected by comparable Ψ_m and Ψ_o ,
14 although their free energy measurements are equal (Hillel, 1972; Schmidhalter and
15 Oertli, 1991). Thus, the seeds of different plants (Meiri, 1984; Schmidhalter and Oertli,
16 1991) and several microorganisms (Ramirez *et al.*, 2004; Chowdhury *et al.*, 2011) have
17 been demonstrated to be more sensitive to low Ψ_m than low Ψ_o . However, very little
18 attention has been given to study the impact of Ψ_m and Ψ_o on seed germination of
19 *Orobanche* species.

20 In this study, our objectives were to determinate the influence of temperature (T), water
21 stress (Ψ_t), and type of water stress (Ψ_m and Ψ_o) on seed germination and radicle length
22 of *O. crenata* during both the conditioning and the incubation periods. These results will
23 be of value for development of predictive infection models.

24 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

25 *Orobanche* seeds

26 Seeds were collected from *O. crenata* plants infecting faba beans during 2010 in
27 Córdoba (37.51°N, 4.80°W, elevation of 110 m), southern Spain. Dry seeds were stored
28 in glass containers in the dark at room temperature until use. Before use, seeds were
29 disinfected with formaldehyde as described by González-Verdejo *et al.* (2005). To
30 ensure that all germination requirements other than T and Ψ_t were satisfied, we included

1 exogenous application of 10 ppm GR24, a synthetic germination stimulant (Johnson *et*
 2 *al.*, 1976) that was applied after conditioning period in the three experiments. In
 3 addition, we included untreated GR24 seeds, which were incubated at 20°C at water
 4 potential value of 0 MPa, for assuring that this stimulant, is needed to seed germination
 5 in *O. crenata*.

6 *Water potential treatments*

7 Because Polyethylene glycol (PEG) solutions are relatively non-toxic to seeds (Song *et*
 8 *al.*, 2005), aqueous solutions of PEG 8000 (Sigma 25322-68-3) or Milli-Q water were
 9 used for producing a range of matric potentials (0, -0.3, -0.6, -0.9, -1.2 and - 3 MPa).
 10 The amount of PEG required for each combination T - Ψ_t was calculated using the
 11 polynomial equation of Michel and Kaufmann (1973) and revised by Michel (1983).

12 Likewise, sterile milli-Q water was modified osmotically by the addition of nonionic
 13 glycerol (Panreac 56-81-5) to 0, -0.3, -0.6, -0.9, -1.2 and -3 MPa (Dallyn and Fox,
 14 1980). The quantity of glycerol used to adjust the water activity (a_w) of each solution
 15 was calculated using the Norrish's equation (Harris, 1980) modified by Baeza *et al.*
 16 (2010). Finally, for a sample at given T, the Ψ_t was uniquely related to the a_w through
 17 the Kelvin equation:

$$\Psi_t = \frac{RT_k}{M_w} \ln a_w \quad (1)$$

18 where R is the universal gas constant, T_k is Kelvin temperature and M_w is the molecular
 19 mass of water (Papendick and Campbell, 1980).

20 The Ψ_t of all solutions was then confirmed by measurement in a dewpoint potentiometer
 21 (WP4 Aqua Lab Water Meter, Decagon Devices, Washington, USA) and subjected to a
 22 slight adjustment when necessary.

23 *Effect of temperature and water potential during the conditioning period*

24 *Experiment 1.* Around 150 seeds of *O. crenata* were sown per 10-mm discs of glass
 25 fiber filter paper (WHATMAN 3645, 175 g m⁻²). Three discs (pseudoreplicates) were
 26 placed in a sterile 5-cm Petri dish lined with two layers of 50-mm diameter glass filter

1 paper wetted with 1.5 mL of sterile milli-Q water or different conditioning media as
2 described by Song *et al.* (2005). These media were PEG or glycerol solutions at -0.3, -
3 0.6, -0.9, -1.2 and -3 MPa. The Petri dishes were sealed with Parafilm and wrapped with
4 aluminum foil to provide absolute darkness. The Petri dishes were then placed in
5 growth chambers at different temperatures (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35°C). After 5
6 days, other 0.6 mL of sterile water or conditioning medium was added to each Petri dish
7 to maintain the Ψ_t and the dishes were placed in the chambers for two conditioning days
8 more.

9 After conditioning, the seeds were blotted to remove excessive water or conditioning
10 media. Each disc from every replicate Petri dish were then transferred to a separate new
11 5-cm Petri dish containing two layers of filter paper wetted with 1.2 mL of sterile milli-
12 Q water with 10 ppm GR24. Petri dishes were incubated at 20°C in the dark as describe
13 above. Germination was examined under a compound microscope (Nikon Eclipse 80i;
14 Nikon Corp., Tokyo) at 7 days after GR24 addition counting around 200 seeds per Petri
15 dish. In addition, we randomly selected 30-40 germinated seeds per treatment and the
16 length of their emerging radicle was also measured at this time. In total, 84 treatments
17 [seven temperatures \times six Ψ_t \times two types of water stress (Ψ_m and Ψ_o)] were evaluated.
18 In all experiments, for each treatment, three replicate Petri dishes were used and the
19 experiment was carried out twice.

20 *Experiment 2.* This experiment was similar to our previous experiment but seed
21 germination was assessed periodically at 2, 7, 10, 20 and 40 days after GR24 addition
22 allowing calculation of seed germination percentage. Conditioning temperature was
23 fixed to 20°C, maintaining the PEG and glycerol solutions at -0.3, -0.6, -0.9, -1.2 and -3
24 MPa. In this case, between 0.1 and 0.3 mL of sterile water or conditioning medium was
25 periodically added to each Petri dish to maintain the Ψ_t .

26 Because the germinated seeds were removed to measure the size of the radicles at 7, 20
27 and 40 days, this evaluation corresponds to seeds germinated between 0-7, 8-20 and 21-
28 40 conditioning days (*see evaluation*). Therefore, the radicle of seeds that germinated
29 between the 10th to 20th days had 10 days to develop, and those that germinated between
30 the 20th and 40th day had 20 days to develop. In total, the seeds were subjected to 12
31 treatments [six Ψ_t \times two types of water stress (Ψ_m and Ψ_o)] that were evaluated after
32 five conditioning periods.

1 *Effect of temperature and water potential during the incubation period*

2 *Experiment 3.* This experiment was similar to *experiment 1* except that *O. crenata* seeds
3 were conditioned at 20°C in the dark for 10 days on the paper discs with sterile distilled
4 water (160 µL per disc). Then the discs were blotted and transferred to new Petri dishes
5 containing filter paper wetted with 1.2 mL of PEG or glycerol solution (-0.3, -0.6, -0.9,
6 -1.2 and -3 MPa). Petri dishes were then incubated at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35°C in
7 the dark. The seed germination was evaluated at 7 and 10 days and the length of the
8 emerging radicle of 30-40 seeds at 7 days as described above. In this case, 84
9 treatments [seven T × six Ψ_t × two types of water stress (Ψ_m and Ψ_o)] were evaluated
10 and the experiment was conducted twice.

11 *Evaluation*

12 In all cases, the germination of *O. crenata* seeds were directly quantified on the Petri
13 dishes using a magnification of 40× with the aid of a compound microscope (Nikon
14 Eclipse 80i; Nikon Corp., Tokyo). For that, we counted the total of seeds of several
15 fields of view that was taken at random. Seeds were considered germinated when the
16 length of the emerging radicle was equal to or longer than its width. Length of the
17 emerging radicle of seed was measured at 200× with the aid of a compound microscope
18 using the NIS-Element software (Nikon Corp., Tokyo, Japan).

19 *Statistical analysis*

20 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed on germination percentage or radicle
21 length depending on the design of each experiment. Both germination percentage and
22 radicle length were log or arcsin-transformed when necessary for normality or
23 homogeneity of variances. All experiments were repeated at once, and data from
24 repetitions of each experiment were combined after checking for homogeneity of the
25 experimental error variances by the *F* test (two variances). Because there were several
26 interactions among independent variables (*experiments 1* and *3*), to clarify the effects of
27 Ψ_t (water vs. negative potentials) or type of water stress (osmotic vs. matric) on the
28 dependent variables, we compared among them using orthogonal contrasts. When the
29 type of water stress did not affect to type of water stress, ANOVA or regression analysis
30 was performed on the whole of data using this variable as repetitions.

1 Linear regression analysis was used to evaluate the relationship between duration of
 2 conditioning period (days) and the cumulative germination percentage (*experiment 2*).
 3 The duration of the conditioning period (days) was log-transformed. Various linear and
 4 nonlinear regression models were evaluated for describing the effect of T and Ψ_t on
 5 seed germination and radicle length during the conditioning and the incubation periods
 6 (*experiments 1 and 3*). The models tested were the generalized Analytis β model (Hau
 7 and Kranz, 1990), the Schödter angular model (Hau and Kranz, 1990), the Yin's model
 8 (Yin *et al.*, 1995) and several second- or third-order polynomial equations based on
 9 results of ANOVA analysis. We included the Ψ_t on the models as $(\Psi_t - \Psi_{min})^c$ when
 10 necessary. The used models were developed with an empirical approach according to
 11 the collected data. These models have been used to describe the influence of
 12 temperature and water stress on germination of broomrape seeds for the first time.

13 The Analytis β model (Hau and Kranz, 1990) was selected because it provided a good
 14 fit for all experiments and because each parameter has biological meaning. The Analytis
 15 β model uses the following equation:

$$16 \quad Y = k \times t^a \times (1 - t)^b \times (\Psi_t - \Psi_{min})^c \quad (2)$$

17 in which Y = standardized germination percentage or radicle length that varied from 0
 18 to 1 ($Y = G/G_{max}$ or $Y = RS/RS_{max}$); t = standardized temperature [$t = (T - T_{min}) / (T_{max} -$
 19 $T_{min})$]; Ψ_t = water potential ($0 \geq \Psi_t \geq \Psi_{min}$); and k , a , b , and c are unknown parameters.
 20 T_{min} , T_{max} , and Ψ_{min} were the minimum temperature, maximum temperature, and
 21 minimum Ψ_t for seed germination, respectively. Maximum Y is reached when
 22 standardized $t = a / (a + b)$. Thus, for a given Ψ_t , if the parameter $a < b$ or $a > b$, the
 23 optimum temperature is shifted to the left or right, respectively. In this study, T_{min} and
 24 T_{max} were selected according to the data of our study, and the Ψ_{min} used on the models (-
 25 2 MPa) was selected according to previous experiments. A linear regression was applied to
 26 test the relationship between data estimated by nonlinear regression and observed data.
 27 In all cases, the best regression model was chosen from many combinations of terms
 28 based on the significance of the estimated parameters ($P \leq 0.05$), Mallows' C_p statistic,
 29 Akaike's information criterion modified for small data sets, the coefficient of
 30 determination (R^2), R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom (R_a^2), and the pattern of residuals
 31 over predicted and independent variables.

1 RESULTS

2 Both T and Ψ_t affected the germination of *O. crenata* seeds during conditioning and
3 incubation periods. Overall, the seeds germinated in a range of T between 10 and 25°C
4 during conditioning (Fig. 1) and incubation (Fig. 5) periods, being germination strongly
5 reduced at 25°C. On the contrary, no germination occurred at 5 or 35°C or under -3 MPa
6 at any temperature and it was very limited at 30°C. For this reasons, equations of
7 models were developed in all cases considering 5 and 30°C as T_{min} and T_{max} ,
8 respectively (Table 1). Moreover, there were several double and triple interactions
9 among the independent variables depending on the experiments. No *O. crenata* seeds
10 untreated with GR24 germinated.

11 *Effect of temperature and water potential during the conditioning period*

12 *Experiment 1.* Seeds of *O. crenata* conditioned in water potentials ≥ -1.2 MPa
13 germinated over the glass fibre filter papers at temperatures between 10 and 25°C.
14 However, when conditioned at $\Psi_t = -1.2$ MPa the seeds did not germinate at 10°C.
15 Maximum seed germination approached 41% in water at 20°C. The germination
16 percentage of seeds conditioned in water was significantly (orthogonal contrasts, $P =$
17 0.035) higher than that of the seeds conditioned in negative water potentials.
18 Conversely, the both matric and osmotic stress have similar (orthogonal contrasts, $P =$
19 0.6318) impact on the germination percentage of the seeds. For example, the mean of
20 seed germination for the seeds conditioned at 20°C among -0.3 and -1.2 MPa under
21 osmotic or matric stress were 25.9 and 23.7%, respectively. For that, the data from each
22 type of water stress were used as independent repetitions to fit the models (Table 1).
23 The fitted Analytis β model of Ψ_t -T affecting the germination percentage is illustrated in
24 Fig. 1. The fitted model was highly significant ($P < 0.001$; R^2 and Ra^2 were > 0.90) and
25 the standardized residuals were randomly distributed over predicted values. The
26 optimum T for maximum seed germination, obtained with fitted model, was 18.9°C.
27 Thus, germination higher than 40% is only obtained with a conditioning at 17 - 20°C at
28 water potential value of 0 MPa (Fig. 1).

29 The effect of T on radicle length followed a similar trend as percentage of seed
30 germination, although showing an optimum temperature lower. The largest radicle
31 lengths were observed at 15 and 20°C for seed conditioned at water potential value of 0

1 MPa, which showed mean radicle lengths $1170 \pm 75 \mu\text{m}$ and $826 \pm 31 \mu\text{m}$, respectively.
2 For lower or higher temperatures the radicle lengths were shorter than previous one.
3 Water potential (water vs. negative potentials) and the types (matric vs. osmotic stress)
4 of water stress had significant (orthogonal contrast, $P < 0.001$) effect on radicle length
5 of germinated seeds of *O. crenata*. Overall, the radicle length increased with increasing
6 of Ψ_t from -1.2 to 0 MPa. Even so, the radicle length of seeds that were conditioned
7 under osmotic stress ($467 \pm 11 \mu\text{m}$) was significantly shorter (orthogonal contrast, $P <$
8 0.001) than those conditioned under matric stress ($652 \pm 12 \mu\text{m}$). For this reason, two
9 regression models were independently fitted for the data of each type of water stress.
10 The Analytis β model showed an excellent fit for the radicle length data of both type of
11 water stress (Table 1). The fitted models were highly significant ($P < 0.001$; R^2 and Ra^2
12 were > 0.84) and the standardized residuals were randomly distributed over predicted
13 values. The predicted optimum temperatures for maximum radicle length were around
14 18.5°C under both types of water stress. According to both fitted models, only the seed
15 that were conditioned in water showed a radicle length over $900 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 2A, B; Table
16 1).

17 *Experiment 2.* *O. crenata* seeds conditioned at 20°C and $\Psi_t \geq -1.2$ MPa during 40 days,
18 germinated under both types of water stress. No seeds germinated when they were
19 conditioned at -3 MPa. Maximum germination ($57.60 \pm 4.5\%$) was obtained for seeds
20 conditioned in water at the end of experiment (Fig. 3). The germination percentage was
21 significantly (orthogonal contrasts, $P = 0.022$) lower at negative potentials than water,
22 but there was not significant differences between both types of water stress (orthogonal
23 contrasts, $P = 0.411$). For this reason, we used the data from each type of water stress as
24 repetitions to fit regression lines (Fig. 3). The cumulative percentage germination
25 increased log-linearly ($R^2 = 0.706$; $P < 0.001$) with increasing of length of the
26 conditioning period from 0 to 40 days (Fig. 3). The short conditioning period that
27 resulted in seed germination was the 7 days, with a germination percentage of $\approx 18\%$ for
28 the seeds conditioned in water. The comparison among the linear regression lines of
29 each Ψ_t (between -1.2 and 0 MPa) showed equality of variances ($P = 0.715$), with
30 significant differences between elevations ($P < 0.001$) but not ($P = 0.475$) among
31 slopes ($b =$ the apparent rate of germination increase). Thus, significant differences
32 were found in the line slopes of water potentials 0 and -1.2 MPa ($P < 0.05$), which were

1 significantly different ($P < 0.05$) to the remaining water potentials that formed a
2 homogeneous group ($P > 0.05$) (Fig. 3).

3 The mean radicle length of *O. crenata* seeds germinated in water during the first week
4 ranged $1165 \pm 68 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 4). The effects of type of water stress, germination period
5 and different interactions among independent variable (type of water stress-germination
6 period and type of water stress-germination period- Ψ_t) on the radicle length were
7 significant ($P < 0.05$). The radicle length of the seeds conditioned in water (863 ± 28
8 μm) was higher (orthogonal contrast, $P < 0.001$) than radicle length of seeds ($605.2 \pm$
9 $9.5 \mu\text{m}$) conditioned in negative water potentials. Moreover, the type of water stress
10 also had significant ($P < 0.001$) effect on the radicle length being 725 ± 13 and $484 \pm$
11 $11 \mu\text{m}$ under matric and osmotic stress, respectively. Overall, seeds germinated during
12 the first days of the conditioning period showed a larger radicle than the later
13 germinated ones. In the case of seeds conditioned in osmotic solutions, however, the
14 seeds conditioned at -0.9 and -1.2 MPa showed a radicle length roughly constant (Fig.
15 4A, B).

16 *Effect of temperature and water potential during incubation period*

17 *Experiment 3.* The germination percentage of conditioned seeds increased with
18 increasing incubation period from 5 to 10 days. The maximum germination percentage
19 increased with the T between 10 and 20°C and then decreased between 20 and 30°C.
20 Likewise, the final germination percentage increased with increasing Ψ_t from -1.2 to 0
21 MPa, approaching around 43% in water at 15°C (Fig. 5). The germination percentage of
22 conditioned seeds incubated in water was significantly higher (orthogonal contrasts, $P <$
23 0.001) than other incubated at negative potentials. On the contrary, there was no
24 significant (orthogonal contrasts, $P = 0.107$) differences on the maximum germination
25 percentage of conditioned seeds that incubated under matric or osmotic stress. The
26 Analytis β equations (Table 1; Fig. 5) fitted satisfactorily to the data of final
27 germination percentage at each T- Ψ_t combination ($P < 0.001$; R^2 and $Ra^2 > 0.93$). The
28 standardized residuals were randomly distributed over predicted again. The obtained-
29 optimum T for seed germination was 19.5°C (Table 1; Fig. 5).

30 Radicle length of seeds of *O. crenata* was highly affected by Ψ_t and T during the
31 incubation period. For example, in the case of seeds incubated in water, average radicle

1 length increased gradually from 304 μm at 10°C until a maximum of 1991 μm at 25°C
2 (Fig. 6). In addition, the conditioned seeds, which were incubated in water, showed
3 higher (orthogonal contrasts, $P < 0.001$) radicle length than other incubated at negative
4 water potentials. The type of water stress had too significant (orthogonal contrasts, $P <$
5 0.001) effect on the radicle length of seeds, being higher ($1150 \pm 588 \mu\text{m}$) in the seeds
6 incubated in PEG solutions than other ($975 \pm 498 \mu\text{m}$) incubated in glycerol solutions.
7 The curves describing the effect of Ψ_t and T on the radicle length of *O. crenata* seeds
8 fitted satisfactorily ($P < 0.001$; R^2 and $Ra^2 > 0.95$) for each type of water stress (Fig. 6A,
9 B). The obtained optimum temperatures for radicle growth were 22.3 and 24.5°C under
10 matric or osmotic stress, respectively (Fig 6A, B; Table 1). The same results were
11 obtained when we studied the germination percentage at 7 incubation days.

12 **DISCUSSION**

13 It has widely acknowledged that germination of *Orobanche* spp. seeds is influenced by
14 environmental and microbiological factors, including T, Ψ_t (Kebreab and Murdoch,
15 1999; 2000; Song *et al.*, 2005) as well as by microbe interactions in the rhizosphere
16 (Mabrouk *et al.*, 2007; Fernández-Aparicio *et al.*, 2010). Traditionally, physiology-
17 based models have been used to describe the effect of the environmental parameters on
18 the germination of *Orobanche* seeds, although they have not been used to radicle length
19 and have additional limitations. For example, the hydrothermal time model
20 (Gummerson, 1986) requires daily evaluations for a good calculation of its rate of
21 germination and it assumes that there is no interaction between Ψ_t and T. Kebreab and
22 Murdoch (1999) proposed an alternative model to explain the interaction of Ψ_t and T,
23 although it predicts that the seed population will eventually achieve 100% germination,
24 which is not the case. To overcome this limitation, they later refined the model
25 (Kebreab and Murdoch, 2000). Even so, hydrothermal time is currently the most used
26 model to study seed germination of different weeds (Finch-Savage and Leubner-
27 Metzger, 2006; Guillemin *et al.*, 2013). Here we studied the effects of T, type of water
28 stress (matric or osmotic) and Ψ_t on seed germination and radicle length of *O. crenata*
29 seeds before and after exposure to GR24 as necessary exogenous stimulus for *O.*
30 *crenata* germination in the absence of an appropriate host. For this purpose, we used the
31 Analytis β model (Hau and Kranz, 1990) that has a series of advantages: i) it provided
32 an excellent fit for germination of *O. crenata* seeds after conditioning period and during

1 the incubation period; ii) it showed a good fit for radicle length of the seeds; and iii) its
2 parameters T_{min} , T_{max} and Ψ_{min} have biological significance, although it is mainly
3 empirical model. Even so, empirical approach may be satisfactory for ecological
4 modelling of seed germination (Forcella *et al.*, 2000). Furthermore, mechanistic risk
5 models can be easily developed considering the normalized rates of seed germination
6 and radicle growth during conditioning and incubation periods using the Analytis β
7 model. To develop mechanistic models, the main steps of the parasite life cycle
8 *Orobanch* spp. (i.e. germination, radicle elongation to the host root, penetration,
9 establishment, and plant develop) can be organized in a relational diagram according to
10 the principles of the “systems analysis” and considering the normalized rates of the
11 these steps (Leffelaar and Ferrari, 1989).

12 As a new feature, we studied separately the impact of both matric and osmotic stresses
13 on seed germination of this parasitic plant due to little attention have been paid to the
14 differences between both stresses. For example, different authors have considered that
15 the water stress caused by PEG solutions is of osmotic type (Kebreab and Murdoch,
16 2000; Song *et al.*, 2005); although it has been previously shown that the water potential
17 generated by PEG is predominantly (99%) due to matric forces (Steuter *et al.*, 1981).

18 During the conditioning period, the maximum germination of *O. crenata* seeds was
19 obtained at 18-21°C. These values are within the optimal range of 15-20°C for
20 germination of *O. crenata* seeds (Van Hezewijk *et al.*, 1993; Kebreab and Murdoch
21 1999; 2000; Song *et al.*, 2005). Small differences on optimum temperature to seed
22 germination could be due to genetic variation within and among populations of *O.*
23 *crenata* that attack legumes in different geographic regions (Van Hezewijk *et al.*, 1993).
24 This is in agreement with the substantial diversity among *O. crenata* populations
25 revealed by molecular analyses (Román *et al.*, 2002). At the optimal temperature for
26 conditioning (20°C), the percentage of germinated seed decreased at both type of water
27 stress from 0 to -1.2 MPa, which is near to permanent wilting point of soil that is
28 reached at -1.5 MPa (Cassel and Nielsen, 1986). Conversely, the seed germination was
29 totally prevented at Ψ_t of -2 MPa in previous experiments. Our results are in agreement
30 with Kebreab and Murdoch (2000) who showed a reduction in *O. aegyptiaca* seed
31 germination when the water potential decreases from 0 to -1.33 MPa. Conversely, Song
32 *et al.* (2005) did not observe significant decrease from 0 to -1 MPa in *O. aegyptiaca* and

1 *O. ramosa* seed germination; although both species showed a marked reduction in seed
2 germination at -2 MPa. It is interesting to remark that for some species as *O. ramosa*,
3 the duration of conditioning period influences on the Ψ_t effect. Thus, the percentage of
4 seed germination of this species is close to zero when the seeds are conditioned at -2
5 MPa during 4 days, and it is around 77% for the seed conditioned during 20 days
6 (Gibot-Leclerc *et al.*, 2004).

7 Even though the radicle elongation of seeds is an essential step in the parasite life cycle
8 of *Orobanchae* species, it has been scarcely studied when compared with seed
9 germination. These studies have focused on the effect of environmental and
10 microbiological factors on radicle elongation. Thus, Westwood and Foy (1999)
11 observed that radicle of *Orobanchae* seeds are more sensible to nitrogen in ammonium
12 form than nitrate. Barghouthi and Salam (2010) identified potential Biological Control
13 Agents (BCAs), mainly *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* species, which adversely affected
14 radicle elongation of *O. aegyptiaca* and *O. cernua*. The inhibition of radicle elongation
15 of *Orobanchae* seeds have also been identified as a resistance mechanism of red clover
16 (*Trifolium pretense*) that is activated on plants treated with salicylate (Kusumoto *et al.*,
17 2007). *Orobanchae* radicle growth inhibition has also been reported by a number of
18 plants and fungal metabolites (Cimmino *et al.*, 2014, 2015; Fernández-Aparicio *et al.*,
19 2013). Here we found differences in the radicle length of *O. crenata* seeds in response
20 to T, Ψ_t and type of water stress during conditioning period. Radicle length was
21 maximum in the treatment of 15°C/0 MPa. In addition, at a given Ψ_t , radicle length was
22 more sensitive to changes in osmotic than in matric potential. The effect of low osmotic
23 potentials on seed germination and radicle elongation of *O. minor* during conditioning
24 and incubation periods has been observed using NaCl solutions; although it could be
25 due to the toxic effect of ions on seeds (Hassan *et al.*, 2010). In previous reports, matric
26 stress exerts a more negative effect than osmotic stress on germination and seedling
27 growth of different plants such as carrot (Schmidhalter and Oertli, 1991), bean (Meiri,
28 1984), pepper and cotton (Shalhevet and Hsiao, 1986). These results may be explained
29 by the fact that *O. crenata* seeds make up for the water stress in different ways and
30 depending on the type of stress. For example, the plants can easily adjust their Ψ_t using
31 the solutes under a saline medium, while are less effective reducing the Ψ_t under matric
32 stress due to a high metabolic energy requirement (Schmidhalter and Oertli, 1991).
33 Likewise, the fungi are able to reduce their Ψ_t by increasing the concentration of total

1 sugar alcohols, although the patterns of accumulation of sugar alcohols change
2 depending on the type of water stress (Ramirez *et al.*, 2004). In addition, at low Ψ_o ,
3 fungi are also able to uptake solutes to reduce their internal osmotic potential, an
4 unavailable option when the Ψ_t is mainly matric (Jones *et al.*, 2011).

5 In our experiments, percentage of seed germination increased logarithmically with the
6 length of conditioning period during 40 days. This is concordant with the fact that *O.*
7 *crenata* seeds tend to lose primary dormancy after a period of conditioning being
8 maximum after 18-21 days (Van Hezewijk *et al.*, 1993; Kebreab and Murdoch, 2000).
9 Nevertheless, we did not distinguish clearly the secondary dormancy of the *O. crenata*
10 seeds, i.e. a decreased in germination percentage after 21 or 49 days of conditioning at
11 20 and 10-15°C, respectively, as it has been observed for this species by Van Hezewijk
12 *et al.* (1993). According to Kebreab and Murdoch (2000), *O. crenata* seeds, however,
13 showed similar germination percentage when they are conditioned at 20°C during 20-40
14 days, and they need more than 70 conditioning days to enter in a secondary dormancy.
15 The induction of secondary dormancy at low temperature during winter, might explain
16 the decline in *Orobanche* infestation observed by farmers in the case of late sowing
17 (Parker and Riches, 1993). In addition, we have observed that seeds, that need less
18 conditioning time to germinated, show the largest radicles.

19 During incubation period, *O. crenata* seeds germinated in a similar range of
20 temperatures (10-25°C) than that which was required during conditioning, and the
21 thermal optimum was the same (about 20°C). Similar optimum temperatures have been
22 described for this species (Van Hezewijk *et al.*, 1993), *O. aegyptiaca* (Jain and Foy,
23 1992; Kebreab and Murdoch 2000) and *O. ramosa* (Gibot-Leclerc *et al.*, 2004).
24 Likewise, the germination percentage decreased with decreasing of Ψ_t from 0 to -1.2
25 MPa, with no apparent differences between the types of water stress. According to our
26 data, at given temperature (20°C), the percentage of germination of *O. crenata* seeds
27 during conditioning period decrease at 16.4% per MPa, whereas the germination
28 declined a 22.4% per MPa during the incubation. This fact suggests than *O. crenata*
29 seeds appear more sensitive to low levels of Ψ_t during conditioning period than during
30 the subsequent incubation phase. Water stress may be more limiting in the conditioning
31 period, during which it is necessary that water enters into the seeds, than during the

1 incubation period, when the seeds are already hydrated (Finch-Savage and Leubner-
2 Metzger, 2006).

3 The radicle length of *O. crenata* seeds was shorter on the seed incubated in osmotic
4 than matric potentials, which it has been previously discussed. This fact, the high
5 sensibility of radicle elongation to osmotic stress could be related with the lowest
6 infestation of *Orobanch*e spp. in regions characterized by saline soil, as the region south
7 to the Dead Sea in Jordan (Abu Irmaileh, 1998).

8 In summary, the results of this study clearly show that low matric and low osmotic
9 potential had negative impacts on seed germination and radicle length of *O. crenata*
10 seeds. At given Ψ_t , the reduced percentage of seed germination was similar under matric
11 and osmotic stress during the conditioning or incubation period. In contrast, our results
12 show that low Ψ_o had a stronger negative effect on radicle length of *O. crenata* seeds
13 than low Ψ_m during both periods.

14

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1

2 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

3 **Fig. 1.** Effects of temperature (°C) and water potential (MPa) on seed germination of
4 *Orobancha crenata* during conditioning period. The lines were fitted according to
5 Analytis β equation (Hau and Kranz, 1990; Table 1). Points represent the average of 12
6 repetitions. Bars represent the standard deviation of the mean.

7 **Fig. 2.** Effects of temperature (°C) and matric (**A**) or osmotic (**B**) potentials (MPa) on
8 radicle length of *Orobancha crenata* seeds during conditioning period. The lines were
9 fitted according to Analytis β equation (Hau and Kranz, 1990; Table 1). Points represent
10 the average of 6 repetitions. Bars represent the standard deviation of the mean.

11 **Fig. 3.** Cumulative germination percentage of *Orobancha crenata* conditioned at 20°C
12 under different water potentials (MPa) during 40 days. The lines were fitted according
13 to logarithmic equation [$G (\%) = a + \log (\text{days})$] for each water potential. Points
14 represent the average of 12 repetitions. Bars represent the standard deviation of the
15 mean.

16 **Fig. 4.** Effect of the incubation period, during which the *Orobancha crenata* seeds
17 germinated (days after GR24 addition), on the radicle length seeds (μm) under matric
18 (**A**) or osmotic potentials (**B**). Points represent the average of 6 repetitions. Bars
19 represent the standard error of each mean.

20 **Fig. 5.** Effects of temperature (°C) and water potential (MPa) on seed germination of
21 *Orobancha crenata* during incubation period. The lines were fitted according to
22 Analytis β equation (Hau and Kranz, 1990; Table 1). Points represent the average of 12
23 repetitions. Bars represent the standard deviation of the mean.

24 **Fig. 6.** Effects of temperature (°C) and matric (**A**) or osmotic (**B**) potentials (MPa) on
25 radicle length of *Orobancha crenata* seeds during incubation period. The lines were
26 fitted according to Analytis β equation (Hau and Kranz, 1990; Table 1). Points represent
27 the average of 6 repetitions. Bars represent the standard deviation of the mean.

Table 1. Effect of temperature (T), water potential (Ψ_t), and type of water stress [matric (Ψ_m) or osmotic (Ψ_o)] during conditioning (*experiment 1*) and incubation (*experiment 3*) periods on seed germination and radicle length (0-1) of *Orobanche crenata* seeds according to the fitted Analytis β models

Studied period	Y	Water stress	Analytis β model parameters ^{x,y}				R^2	T opt (°C)
			K	a	b	c		
Conditioning	Gemination	Ψ_m and Ψ_o^z	365.071	5.433	4.332	1.016	0.986	18.9
Conditioning	Radicle	Ψ_m	2.393	1.153	0.974	0.595	0.931	18.6
Conditioning	Radicle	Ψ_o	1.588	1.214	1.027	1.222	0.841	18.5
Incubation	Gemination	Ψ_m and Ψ_o^z	3.253	2.032	1.479	1.736	0.941	19.5
Incubation	Radicle	Ψ_m	3.436	1.872	0.821	0.5610	0.983	22.4
Incubation	Radicle	Ψ_o	2.241	1.793	0.663	0.808	0.973	24.0

^xSeed germination or radicle length (Y), temperature (T), and water potential (Ψ_t) data were adjusted to a nonlinear Analytis β model

$Y = k \times t^a \times (1 - t)^b \times (\Psi t - \Psi t_{min})^c$ (Hau and Kranz, 1990), the equations of models were developed in all cases considering 5 and 30°C and -2 MPa as T_{min} , T_{max} and Ψt_{min} , respectively.

^y*O. crenata* seeds were conditioned, before GR24 (conditioning period) addition, at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, and 35°C from -3 to 0 MPa (water) in humid chambers. Likewise, seeds were incubated, after the GR24 (incubation period), in the same conditions.

^zThere was not significant effect of type of water stress (matric or osmotic) on seed germination according to orthogonal contrast at $P < 0.05$.

Figure 1.JPEG

Fig. 1

Figure 2.JPEG

Fig. 2

Figure 3.JPEG

Fig. 3

Figure 4.JPEG

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Figure 6.JPEG

Fig. 6